

The Role of Motivation and Servant Leadership on Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance in the Investment and One-Stop Services Office, Gianyar Regency

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ABSTRACT

Every organization wants its personnel to be committed to the organization and to deliver their best performance. It is known that motivation and servant leadership affect organizational commitment and employee performance. This study investigates and explains the impact of motivation and servant leadership on organizational commitment and employee performance at the Investment and One-Stop Services Office, Gianyar Regency. Quantitative methods are used to test models and instruments developed by previous researchers through inferential statistics using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with SmartPLS 4.0 software. This study's population consisted of 123 employees, and the sample comprised of 51 employees. Purposive random sampling was used in determining the sample. Motivation and servant leadership positively and significantly affect organizational commitment and motivation. Servant leadership also has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Motivation and servant leadership positively and significantly affect employee performance through organizational commitment.

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KEYWORDS: Employee performance, organizational commitment, motivation, servant leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are crucial to the success of an organization or business in the modern era. Therefore, organizational leaders need to find ways or methods to improve the performance of their employees. It is essential because performance reflects a profound enjoyment of the work, allowing for faster work completion and better results. Every employee must perform competently to carry out all assigned tasks and responsibilities. Consequently, excellent employee performance must be a priority for success in all organizations, including regional government organizations.

The Investment and One-Stop Services Office is one of the local government organizations in Gianyar Regency. This organization provides licensing-related services and interacts directly with the community. Therefore, it is expected that employees will deliver the highest quality service. However, based on observational data, it was found that employee performance was not optimal. The 2019-2022 community satisfaction survey reveals that only 82.95 % of the community is satisfied with the performance or services provided by the Gianyar Regency Investment and One-Stop Services Office employees, while 17.05% are dissatisfied.

Moreover, according to target data for Advertising Permits and Building Permits (IMB) for the period of 2021, a large number of tasks assigned to employees were not completed on time. In 2021, merely 65.2% of Advertising Permits and 56.7% of IMB were issued. These issues must be addressed immediately in terms of performance, as employees are expected to provide optimum service to the community better and more professionally.

According to interviews with multiple employees of the Gianyar Regency Investment and One-Stop Services Office, the following was determined. Employee organizational commitment decreases as a result of a lack of motivation from the organization and leaders who rarely listen to employee complaints, leaders who give direct instructions to employees, and leaders who rarely attend meetings with subordinates. This has a negative effect on employee performance.

An empirical study was conducted to determine the impact of motivation and servant leadership on employee performance. It was discovered that there was a gap in the previous research. Raka et al. (2018), Hermawati (2020), and Sapta and Landra (2020) found that motivation has a positive

and significant effect on employee performance. On the other hand, Mulyana et al. (2021) and Linggiallo et al. (2021) found that this had no significant effect.

This discrepancy is also found in the influence of servant leadership on employee performance. Kadarusman and Bunyamin (2021), Winarno and Hermana (2021), and Ekhsan and Aziz (2021) found that servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. However, Bayram and Zoubi (2020) and Pratiwi and Nawangsari (2021) found no significant effect.

This study utilized organizational commitment as a mediating variable in response to the research phenomenon and the gaps in empirical findings. Previous research by Madjid and Samsudin (2021), Melati et al. (2021), and Faruq et al. (2021) on the relationship between motivation and organizational commitment discovered positive and statistically significant results. Previous research by Jang and Kandampully (2018), Winarno and Hermana (2021), and Aggarwal et al. (2021) on the impact of servant leadership on organizational commitment discovered positive and statistically significant results. Similarly, Hasanah and Mujanah (2020), Pakpahan et al. (2020), and Suryanthini et al. (2020) discovered positive and statistically significant relationships between organizational commitment and employee performance.

The entire series of research backgrounds and the gaps in previous studies provided a clear direction regarding the formulation of the problem in this study. The problem formulation is How do motivation and servant leadership influence organizational commitment and employee performance? How does organizational commitment affect employee performance? Moreover, what is the role of organizational commitment in mediating the relationship between motivation and servant leadership on employee performance?

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Goal Setting Theory. According to the goal-setting theory, there is a correlation between the objectives set and employee performance. Goal setting theory is a form of motivation theory. The fundamental premise of this theory is that a person's work behavior is influenced by his/her understanding of goals (what the organization expects of him/her). This theory asserts that an individual's thoughts and intentions dictate his/her behavior. Goal setting theory suggests that if an individual is committed to achieving his/her goals, this will affect his/her actions and the consequences of his/her performance. Based on the goal-setting theory approach, employee performance is assumed to be the objective of this study, with motivation, servant leadership, and organizational commitment as the determining factors. If these factors are applied correctly, employee performance will be achieved

Motivation. Linggiallo et al. (2021) stated that motivation is a condition that occurs in someone who can encourage the relationship between attitudes, needs, and perceptions that influence a person's decision-making. Motivation can also be defined as an energetic force that directs the nature of psychological behavior in employee activities and generates the desire to work optimally to achieve organizational objectives (Melati et al., 2021). According to Basri and Kadir (2019), there are four motivational variable indicators: incentives, work placements, employee attention, and advancement opportunities.

Servant Leadership. According to Pakpahan et al. (2020), servant leadership begins with a person's innate desire to serve first, followed by an aspiration to lead. Setyaningrum et al. (2017) define servant leadership as a leadership style focused on the interests of the people it leads by providing recognition and effort to develop them to complete their work correctly and achieve organizational objectives. Hasanah and Mujanah (2020) identify four variables as indicators of servant leadership: compassion, empowerment, vision, and humility.

Organization Commitment. Winarno and Hermana (2021) state that organizational commitment can be interpreted as a reasonable response to staying in the organization and being involved in efforts to achieve the organization's mission, values, and goals. Organizational commitment can also be interpreted as an employee's trust in the organization, allowing him/her to work independently for the organization without significant coercion (Amalia and Nurafian, 2021). Aggarwal et al. (2021) identify three indicators of organizational commitment variables: affective, continuance, and normative commitments.

Employee Performance. Hasanah and Mujanah (2020) state that employee performance is a function of the interaction process between employee skills and encouragement. Hence, this requires essential consideration because the individual performance of an employee in an organization can be a driving force for the organization's performance. Performance results from a person's achievements in accomplishing tasks based on predetermined criteria (Bennyamin et al. 2021). According to Winarno and Hermana (2021), there are three indicators of employee performance variables: work quality, work quantity, and work efficiency.

The influence of motivation on organizational commitment. Amalia and Nurafian (2021) found a positive and significant influence on motivation and organizational commitment. Further, Faruq et al. (2021) found that motivation results have a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

The influence of servant leadership on organizational commitment. Hasanah and Mujanah (2020) found that servant leadership positively and significantly affects organizational commitment. Aggarwal et al. (2021) also show that there is a positive and significant influence between servant leadership on organizational commitment.

The influence of motivation on employee performance. Benjamin et al. (2021) found that motivation positively and significantly affects employee performance. Sapta and Landra (2020) also obtained the same research results: motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The influence of servant leadership on employee performance. Kadarusman and Bunyamin (2021) found that servant leadership positively and significantly affects performance. Additionally, Winarno and Hermana (2021) also found a positive and significant influence between servant leadership and performance.

The influence of organizational commitment on employee performance. Kotama et al. (2020) found that organizational

commitment positively and significantly affects employee performance. Suryathini et al. (2020) also found that organizational commitment positively and significantly affects employee performance.

The influence of organizational commitment in mediating the relationship between motivation on employee performance. Winda et al. (2022) found that organizational commitment can well mediate employee performance. Frastika and Franksiska (2021) obtain identical outcomes.

The influence of organizational commitment in mediating the relationship between servant leadership on employee performance. Winarno and Hermana (2021) found that organizational commitment can mediate the influence of servant leadership on employee performance. Hasanah and Mujanah (2020) also state that organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between servant leadership and employee performance.

Based on the theoretical study and the results of previous research, a theoretical framework is obtained, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Hypothesis

- H1: Motivation has a positive effect on organizational commitment.
- H2: Servant leadership has a positive effect on organizational commitment.
- H3: Motivation has a positive effect on employee performance.
- H4: Servant leadership has a positive effect on employee performance.

- H5: Organizational commitment has a positive effect on employee performance.
- H6: Organizational commitment has a positive effect in mediating the relationship between motivation and employee performance.
- H7: Organizational commitment has a positive effect in mediating the relationship between servant leadership on employee performance.

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METHOD

Research design. This research is quantitative descriptive research, which uses a certain way of collecting, processing and analyzing existing data and is measured on a numerical scale.

Population and sample. The population in this study consisted of 123 employees of the Gianyar Regency Investment and One-Stop Services Office, with a sample of 51 employees. The sampling method employed was purposive random sampling.

Data Collection Techniques and Instrument Development. This study used a questionnaire as a data collection tool. All research instruments utilize a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly agree = (1)" to "strongly disagree = (5)".

Data analysis technique. The developed models and instruments were tested using inferential statistics using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique and the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach using Smart PLS 4.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Characteristics of Respondents. The characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents

No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Sex		
	a) Male	29	56.9%
	b) Female	22	43.1%
	Total	51	100 %
2	Age		
	a) 30 years - 40 years	5	9.8 %
	b) 41 years - 50 years	23	45.1%
	c) > 50 years	23	45.1%
	Total	51	100 %
3	Education		
	a) Senior High School/Equivalent	6	11.8%
	b) S1	32	62.7%
	c) S2	13	25.5%
	Total	51	100 %
4	Years of service		
	a) < 10 years	24	47.1%
	b) 11 years - 20 years	19	37.3%
	c) > 20 years	8	15.7%
	Total	51	100 %

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

According to Table 1, there are 66.9% more male respondents than female respondents. Regarding age, it is known that the largest proportion of respondents, 45.1%, are between the ages of 41 and 50, followed by those older than 50. Regarding recent education, the majority, 62.7%, are bachelor's degree graduates. When viewed from the length of

service, the dominant employee has a service period of <10 years, which is as much as 47.1%.

Validity test. In the validity test, there are two tests, namely the convergent validity test and the discriminant validity test. The results of the convergent validity test are shown in the graph below.

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Table 2. Results of the Convergent Validity Test

Variable	Original (O)	Sample T statistics ((O/STDEV))	T Tabel	Information
X1.1 <- Motivation	0.920	45.008	1.96	Valid
X1.2 <- Motivation	0.880	34.122	1.96	Valid
X1.3 <- Motivation	0.886	28.783	1.96	Valid
X1.4 <- Motivation	0.880	31.709	1.96	Valid
X2.1 <- Servant Leadership	0.883	28.988	1.96	Valid
X2.2 <- Servant Leadership	0.837	23.065	1.96	Valid
X2.3 <- Servant Leadership	0.843	24.939	1.96	Valid
X2.4 <- Servant Leadership	0.899	40.178	1.96	Valid
Y1.1 <- Organizational Commitment	0.827	19.058	1.96	Valid
Y1.2 <- Organizational Commitment	0.913	46.760	1.96	Valid
Y1.3 <- Organizational Commitment	0.870	25.618	1.96	Valid
Y2.1 <- Employee Performance	0.865	20.022	1.96	Valid
Y2.2 <- Employee Performance	0.896	30.007	1.96	Valid
Y2.3 <- Employee Performance	0.905	34.601	1.96	Valid

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

Table 2 shows that the indicators for measuring the variables of motivation, servant leadership, organizational commitment and employee performance have an outer loading value of

more than 0.7. Therefore, all indicators of research variables are valid. The results of the discriminant validity test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of the Discriminant Validity Test

Variable	AVE	√AVE	Correlation			
Employee Performance (Y2)	0.790	0.889	0.889			
Organizational Commitment (Y1)	0.759	0.871	0.856	0.871		
Motivation (X1)	0.795	0.892	0.825	0.813	0.892	
Servant Leadership (X2)	0.750	0.866	0.825	0.847	0.772	0.866

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

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Table 3 shows that the results of the four research variables have an AVE value above 0.50, and all variables have a root AVE value higher than the correlation coefficient between one variable and another. Therefore, the data has good discriminant validity.

Reliability Test. In the reliability test, composite reliability testing was carried out. The results of the composite reliability test are presented in Table 4

Table 4. Results of the Composite Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	Information
Employee Performance (Y2)	0.867	0.873	Reliabel
Organizational Commitment (Y1)	0.841	0.849	Reliabel
Motivation (X1)	0.914	0.917	Reliabel
Servant Leadership (X2)	0.888	0.890	Reliabel

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

Table 4 indicates that all variables have composite reliability because their values exceed 0.70 and Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.60. Thus it can be concluded that all indicators of research variables have met the reliability

criteria.

R-Square value. The coefficient of determination (R-Square) of each dependent variable is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. R-Square Value

Structural Model	Variable	R-Square
1	Organizational Commitment	0.781
2	Employee Performance	0.800
$Q^2 \text{ Calculation}$ $Q^2 = 1 - [(1 - R^2_1)(1 - R^2_2)]$ $Q^2 = 1 - [(1 - 0.781)(1 - 0.800)]$ $Q^2 = 1 - [(0.219)(0.200)]$ $Q^2 = 1 - 0.044$ $Q^2 = 0.956$		

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

Based on Table 5, the evaluation of the structural model has a Q2 value of 0.956, close to 1. It provides evidence that the structural model has a good Goodness of Fit Model. This result indicates that 95.6% of the data's information can be explained by the model, while the remaining 4.4% can be explained by error or other variables not included in the model.

Hypothesis testing. Table 6 shows the results of hypothesis testing, which states that all hypotheses are accepted. The results of this hypothesis test inform that H1 (T Statistics > 1.96; = 0.394), namely motivation, has a positive and

significant effect on organizational commitment. H2 (T Statistics > 1.96; = 0.543), namely servant leadership, positively and significantly affects organizational commitment. H3 (T Statistics > 1.96; = 0.316), namely motivation, has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. H4 (T Statistics > 1.96; = 0.259), namely servant leadership, positively and significantly affects employee performance. The last hypothesis, H5 (T-Statistics > 1.96; = 0.379), is accepted, indicating organizational commitment positively and significantly affects employee performance.

Table 6. Results of the Direct Influence Test

Variable	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Information
Motivation -> Organizational Commitment	0.394	4.448	0.000	Signifikan
Servant Leadership -> Organizational Commitment	0.543	6.455	0.000	Signifikan
Motivation -> Employee Performance	0.316	3.141	0.002	Signifikan

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Servant Leadership -> Employee Performance	0.259	2.143	0.032	Signifikan
Organizational Commitment -> Employee Performance	0.379	2.740	0.006	Signifikan

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

Mediation Testing. Hair et al. (2006) provide guidelines for examining the mediating role of variables, such as; (a) examining the direct effect of independent variables on the dependent variable in the model involving mediating variables; (b) examining the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable in the model without involving mediating variables; (c) examine the effect of independent variables on mediating variables; and (d) examining the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable. There is one variable that mediates the effect of motivation and servant leadership on employee performance, namely

organizational commitment. Table 6 shows that significantly organizational commitment acts as a partial mediation based on characteristics; the effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable (c) and the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable (d) is significant, the effect of the independent variable directly on the dependent variable of the model involving the mediating variable (a) is significant, and the independent variable directly affects the dependent without involving the mediating variable (b) significant, so that the organizational commitment variable acts as a partial mediation.

Table 7. Summary of Results from Mediation Testing

No	Path	Path Mediation	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	Information
1	Motivation -> Employee Performance	Motivation -> Organization Commitment -> Employee Performance	0.316 (sig)	0.468 (sig)	0.394 (sig)	0.379 (sig)	Partial Mediasi
2	Servant leadership -> Employee Performance	Servant Leadership -> Organization Commitment -> Employee Performance	0.259 (sig)	0.465 (sig)	0.543 (sig)	0.379 (sig)	Partial Mediasi

Source: Results of data processing, 2023

Based on direct hypothesis testing and mediation testing, it can be concluded:

- Hypothesis 1 : Motivation has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment
- Hypothesis 2 : Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment
- Hypothesis 3 : Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
- Hypothesis 4 : Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
- Hypothesis 5 : Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
- Hypothesis 6 : Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment
- Hypothesis 7 : Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Motivation on Organizational Commitment

Statistical analysis of the data shows that motivation has a positive and significant effect on organizational

commitment. This research model shows that high motivation will lead to high employee organizational commitment. Motivation is an energetic impulse that directs the character of psychological behavior in employee activities, creating enthusiasm to work optimally to achieve organizational goals. This statement emphasizes a close relationship between motivation and organizational commitment (Melati et al., 2021). This study's results align with Al-Madi et al. (2017) regarding the effect of employee motivation on organizational commitment. They found that motivation had a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Apart from that, Amalia and Nurafian (2021) also found motivation's positive and significant influence on organizational commitment.

The Influence of Servant Leadership on Organizational Commitment

Statistical data analysis shows that servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This research model shows that good servant leadership will lead to high employee organizational commitment. Servant leadership is a leadership style oriented to the interests of the people it leads by providing recognition and effort to develop it to work well (Setyaningrum et al., 2017). This study's results align with research from Hasanah

and Mujanah (2020) regarding the influence of servant leadership on organizational commitment at the Bangkalan Regency Public Works Service. They found that servant leadership positively and significantly affected organizational commitment. In addition, the results of another study by Aggarwal et al. (2021) also show servant leadership's positive and significant influence on organizational commitment.

The Influence of Motivation on Employee Performance

Statistical data analysis indicates that motivation positively and significantly affects employee performance. This research model analysis demonstrates that high employee motivation will result in high performance. Motivation is one of the most important factors that organizations must consider to encourage employees to be enthusiastic about their work and thus better their performance. The findings of this study concur with those of Benyamin et al. (2021), who discovered that motivation has a positive and statistically significant effect on employee performance. In addition, research conducted by Hermawati (2020) on the effect of motivation on the performance of PT. Mandiri Utama Sejahtera employees demonstrates a positive and statistically significant relationship between motivation and employee performance.

The Influence of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Statistical data analysis indicates that servant leadership positively and significantly affects employee performance. This research model shows that high servant leadership will lead to high employee performance. Servant leadership is important in supporting employee work processes that can improve their performance. Servant leadership is a leadership style that concentrates on employees rather than organizational results. Its primary objective is to serve followers so that when employees feel valued, thus, their performance can improve. This study's results align with Kadarusman and Bunyamin (2021) regarding the influence of servant leadership on the performance of STIE Malangucwara employees, who discovered that servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance. In addition, research conducted by Winarno and Hermana (2021) on how to encourage lecturer performance through servant leadership demonstrates a positive and statistically significant relationship between servant leadership and lecturer performance.

The Influence of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

Statistical data analysis indicates that organizational commitment positively and significantly affects employee performance. This research model shows that high organizational commitment will lead to high employee performance. Organizational commitment is the attitude of an employee who demonstrates loyalty to the organization and

how employees will care about their organization, thereby enhancing their performance. The results of this study align with Kotama et al. (2020) regarding the impact of organizational commitment on employee performance, which obtained that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Another study by Suryanthini et al. (2020) also obtained the same result: organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The Influence of Motivation on Employee Performance

Indirect testing of the variable motivation on employee performance through organizational commitment shows that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment. Winda et al. (2022) stated that organizational commitment plays an important role in mediating the influence of motivation on performance. It suggests that commitment can explain the relationship between motivation and performance. The findings of this study concur with those of Frastika and Franksiska (2021), who discovered that organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between employee motivation and performance. The same conclusion was reached by Winda et al. (2022) in their study titled The Impact of Motivation on the Performance of Employees Managing the Denpasar City Garbage Bank.

The Influence of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance

Indirect testing of the servant leadership variable on employee performance through organizational commitment shows that servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through organizational commitment. According to Setyaningrum et al. (2017), applying servant leadership in organizations can motivate employees to participate, work voluntarily, and encourage performance. Servant leadership, besides directly producing employee performance, can also build organizational commitment for employees. This result is in line with Hasanah and Mujanah (2020), which state that organizational commitment can mediate the influence of servant leadership on employee performance. It is also supported by Winarno and Hermana (2021) that organizational commitment can mediate the influence of servant leadership on employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Motivation is the most dominant factor in influencing employee performance, so it is expected that the organization will be able to provide high motivation to its employees. In motivation, namely the incentive indicator, it is known to have the highest value. Based on this, it is hoped that the Investment and One-Stop Service Office of Gianyar Regency will pay more attention to the accuracy of incentive

disbursements so that every employee will be motivated and produce better work.

The servant leadership variable, namely the humility indicator, has the highest average value. Based on this, it is expected that the leadership of the Investment and One-Stop Service Office of Gianyar Regency will be open to accepting differences of opinion and willing to listen to criticism and suggestions given by employees. It will assist employees in resolving problems, thereby enhancing employee performance.

The variable organizational commitment, namely, the indicator of sustainable commitment, is known to have the highest value. Based on this, it is expected that the Investment and One-Stop Service Office of Gianyar Regency will focus more on meeting the needs of its employees. It is necessary to have a policy related to compensation given to employees so that, from an economic standpoint, employees feel that their needs are fulfilled.

Employee performance variables, namely work efficiency indicators, are known to have the highest value. Based on this, the Investment and One-Stop Service Office of Gianyar Regency is expected to evaluate the available facilities, both facilities and infrastructure. It is necessary to ensure the feasibility of these facilities in order to support the speed of completion of tasks assigned to employees.

REFERENCES

1. Aggarwal, A., Kamrunnisha, N., Jaisinghani., & Sharma, G. (2021). Analysing the mediating effect of leader-member exchange on the relationship between servant leadership and organisational commitment. *International Journal Economics and Business Research*, Vol. 21 (2), 287-303.
2. Al-Madi, F. N., Assal, H., Shrafat, F., & Zeglat, D. (2017), The Impact of Employee Motivation on Organizational Commitment. *Europen Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 9 (15), 134-145.
3. Amalia, L., & Nurafian, B. (2021), Model Of Correlation Of Work Motivation And Organizational Commitment Through Workplace Spirituality And Servant Leadership. *Jurnal Bussines, Management and Bank*, Vol. 7 (1), 1-14.
4. Basri, M., & Kadir, A. (2019). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Iklim Organisasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai pada Lembaga Penjaminan Mutu Pendidikan Provinsi Sulawesi Tenggara [The Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Climate on Employee Performance at the Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Education Quality Assurance Institute]. *Journal Publicuho*, Vol. 2 (1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.35817/jpu.v2i1.5854>. In Indonesian language.
5. Bayram, P., & Zoubi, K. (2020). The effect of servant leadership on employees' self-reported performance: Does public service motivation play a mediating explanatory role?. *Management Science Letters*, Vol. 25, 1771-1776.
6. Benyamin, C., Prasetyo, F. P., & Widjana, A. (2021). Employee Performance Effect In Pt. "X" Company, Under The Impact Of Servant Leadership Style And Motivation. *Dyntax Idea*, Vol. 3 (4), 737-748.
7. Ekhsan, M. & Aziz, A. (2021) Servant Leadership and Employee Performance: Does Organizational Commitment Mediate in the Model?. *Journal ICoGEMT*, 373-382.
8. Faruq, U., Sujanto, B., & Abdullah, T. (2021). The Influence of Work Team, Trust in Superiors and Achievement Motivation on Organizational Commitment of UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau Lecturers. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Vol. 03 (05), 20-33.
9. Frastika, A., & Franksiska, R. (2021). The impact of Motivation and Environment on Employee Performance with organizational Commitment as Intervening Variable. *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, Vol. 5 (4), 551-560. <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/IJSSB/index>
10. Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., Anderson, R., & Tatham, R. (2006). *"Multivariate Data Analysis (6th Ed.)"*. Uppersaddle River, New Jersey, Pearson Prentice Hall.
11. Hasanah, U., & Mujanah, S. (2020). The Effect Of Servant Leadership, Self-Awareness, And Competence On Organizational Commitment And Performance Of Employees Of Public Works In Bangkalan District. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*, Vol. 4 (2), 136- 146.
12. Hermawati, R. (2020). Analysis on The Effect of Compensation, Discipline and Motivation Toward Performance of Employees of Mandiri Utama Sejahtera Corporation. *Jurnal Pemikiran dan Penelitian Administrasi Publik*, Vol. 10 (1), 99-112.
13. Jang, J., & Kandampully, J. (2018). Reducing Employee Turnover Intention Through Servant Leadership in the Restaurant Context: A Mediation Study of Affective Organizational Commitment, Indonesia). *International Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, Vol. 19 (2), 125-141.
14. Kadurasman, K., & Bunyamin, B. (2020). The role of knowledge sharing, trust as mediation on servant leadership and job performance. *Management Science Letters*, Vol. 11, 1509-1520.
15. Kotama, K. B., Sujana, I. W., Landra, N., & Suardhika, I. N. (2020). The Influence of

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- Transformational Leadership and Career Development on Employee Performance with Commitment of the Organization as a Mediation Variable in the Department of Health, Klungkung District, Indonesia. *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*, Vol. 9 (9), 104-119.
16. Linggiallo, H. D., Riadi, S. S., Hariyadi, S., & Adhimursandi, D. (2021). The effect of predictor variables on employee engagement and organizational commitment and employee Performance. *Management Sciences Letters*, Vol. 11, 31-40.
17. Madjid, A., & Samsudin, M. (2021). Impact of Achievement Motivation and Transformational Leadership on Teacher Performance Mediated by Organizational Commitment. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, Vol. 21 (3), 107-119.
18. Melati, B. A., Moeins, A., & Tukiran, M. (2021), The Relationship Between The Organizational Climate And Work Motivation With The Commitment To The Organization In PT. Citra Abadi Sejati. *International Journal of Social Policy and Law*, Vol. 2 (2), 22-36.
19. Mulyana, Y., Chaeroni, N., Erlangga, H., Solahudin, M., Nurjaya, Sunarsi, D., Anggraeni, N., Jamalus, Masriah, I., Yuangga, K. D., & Purwanto, A. (2021). The Influence of Motivation, Ability, Organizational Culture, Work Environment on Teachers Performance. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, Vol. 12 (04), 99-108.
20. Pakpahan, M., Hardianawati, & Suwarlan. (2021). Servant Leadership and Performance Employee: The Mediating Effect of Organizational Commitment. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Vol. 529, 884-892. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>
21. Pratiwi & Nawangsari. (2021). Organizational Citizenship Behavior while mediating Self-Efficacy, Servant Leadership and Organization Culture on Employee Performance. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, Vol. 6 (1), 225-231.
22. Raka, B. I. T., Yuesti, A., & Landra, N. (2018). Effect of Motivation to Employee Performance which was Mediated by Work Satisfaction in PT Smailing Tour Denpasar, *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, Vol. 9 (8), 20959-20973.
23. Sapta, I. K. S., & Landra, N. (2020). Work Motivation as Education Influence Transformational Leadership On Employee Performance At The Lila Cita Sari Mekar Batur Kintamani Bangli Company. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, Vol. 29 (7), 2059-2068.
24. Setyaningrum, R. P., Setiawan, M., & Surachman. (2017). Organizational Commitments Are Mediation of Relationships Between Servant Leadership And Employee Performance. *Journal of Applied Management*, Vol. 15 (4), 693-701.
25. Sugiyono. 2018. *Metode Peneletian Kuantitatif (Mixed Methods)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
26. Suryanthini, P. M., Landra, N., & Agung, A. A. P. (2020). The Influence of Job Stress and Employee Engagement to Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance (Study on PT. Biseka Denpasar), *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, Vol. 11 (8), 21836-21845.
27. Winarno, A. & Hermana, D. (2021). How to encourage lecturer performance in research through servant leadership, organizational commitment, and tacit knowledge sharing. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa*, Vol. 14 (1), 35-48.
28. Winda, M., Susanti, P. H., & Trarintya, M. A. P. (2022). The Role of Commitment to Mediate Effect of Motivation on The Performance of Waste Bank Managers in The City of Denpasar. *Sinomics Journal*, Vol. 1 (2), 115-130.